

Exploring the Impact of Double-Shift and Single-Shift Classes on Academic Progress and Well-Being of Grade I Pupils: An Action Research Study

Eliza R. Calabria
Valencia City Central School
eliza.calabria@deped.gov.ph

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ABSTRACT

The main objectives of the study are to determine the level of academic and classroom performance, classroom social interaction, and the significant differences between Grade I pupils of double-shift and single-shift classes. A descriptive research design was employed to describe the academic performance, classroom performance, and classroom social interaction of pupils in double-shift and single-shift classes. Participants of the study were the 39 Grade I-Petunia, 35 Grade I-Rafflesia, 39 Grade I-Petunia who are in a double-shift class program, 37 Grade I Birds of Paradise pupils, 35 Grade I Sampaguita pupils and 37 Grade I Zinnia pupils who are in the single-shift classes, and the 28 Grade I teachers of Valencia City Central School,

District IA, Division of Valencia City in the first quarter, in the school year 2024-2025. Moreover, Grade I pupils in double-shift and single-shift classes are at the level of developing in academic performance, classroom performance, and classroom social interaction. Finally, no significant differences exist in academic performance, classroom performance, and classroom social interaction in double-shift and single-shift classes.

Keywords: *Impact, Single Shift, Double Shift, Academic Progress, Well Being*

INTRODUCTION

In the realm of modern education, the pursuit of innovative teaching methods and educational strategies is an ongoing endeavor to enhance academic progress and overall well-being of pupils. The recent educational system in elementary education, it continuously evolved in adapting to the changes in society coping with the needs and demands of the pupils. These dynamic shifts and observations have captured the attention of the importance of the implementation of the double-shift classes for grade I pupils. In recent years, elementary schools had alternative school hour schedules as a way to enhance learning outcomes and increase the overall learning experiences of the pupils. Classical single-shift classes were practiced in elementary education, but due to different concerns, the policymakers started to implement double-shift classes with classroom deficiency and presuming that continuous sessions provide good academic outcomes and develop the total personality of pupils. As Walker (2015) stated, double-shift classes relieve stress and make it easier to function throughout the week. With less time to worry about school and grades, it allows students to function better, resulting in a better outcome in the future. Further supported by Mollica (2021) double-shift classes could be used to give students extra time to do work or as a much-needed stress-free time after a long and stressful week of school.

Thus, this action research study is conducted focused on the exploration of double-shift classes on the academic progress and well-being of Grade I pupils. The findings of this action research study have the potential to inform educational policy and practice in elementary schools, offering helpful insights into the benefits and challenges of adaptation to double-shift classes for Grade I pupils. Furthermore, this research comes up with innovative educational strategies aimed at developing holistic, academic excellence, and emotionally stable learners. It is further anticipated that the results of this study will deepen the understanding of the implications of double-shift classes for Grade I pupils as well as provide actionable insights that can guide policymakers, administrators, policymakers, educators, and parents in shaping learners' resilience.

Proposed Innovation, Intervention and Strategy

As early as December 2004, the policy on double shifting of classes was promulgated as a means of addressing the classroom shortage and reducing class sizes. (DepED Order: (No. 64, s. 2004). In a double-shift system, schools cater for two entirely separate groups of pupils during a school day. The first group of pupils usually attends school from early morning until midday, and the second group usually attends from mid-day to late afternoon. Each group uses the same buildings, equipment, and other facilities (Bray, 2018).

This study is anchored in the concept of Katende (2018) that double-shift schooling students can use the extra time to do personal reading, thereby encouraging optimum use of facilities like the library. If administered well, the morning shift can use the afternoon hours for co-curricular studies and vice-versa, hence making learning worth the student's time. Similarly, this study is also anchored in the concept of Bray, (2017) pointed out that evaluators in the Ministry of Education posted a result that the student performance in the classrooms experimenting with the double-shift system, compared to the results of regular classrooms, was positive; student scores in tested areas (reading, writing, numeracy) were generally higher.

METHODS

Formal permission to conduct the research was secured from the school principal. The permission was made for the data-gathering activity official. The researcher will be getting the Mean Percentile Score (MPS) of the pupils from the class advisers of the double-shift and single-shift classes for the first quarter. A teacher-made questionnaire was distributed to the 28 Grade I teachers to determine the well-being of the pupils.

Research Design

Descriptive research design was employed. Descriptive method was used since it was designed to describe the academic performance of Grade I pupils in a single and double shift session classes.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in the Department of Education, Division of Bukidnon, District IA, Valencia City Central School on the school year 2024-2025. The school is managed by the principals and school heads who are assigned in each department headed by a district supervisor.

Participants and Sampling Technique

The participants of the study were the 39 Grade I-Petunia, 35 Grade I-Rafflesia, 39 Grade I-Petunia who are in double-shift classes, 37 Grade I Birds of Paradise pupils, 35 Grade I Sampaguita pupils and 37

Grade I Zinnia pupils who are in the single-shift classes, and the 28 Grade I teachers of Valencia City Central School, District IA, Division of Valencia City in the first quarter, in the school year 2024-2025.

This study focused on the level of mean percentile score and the level of Grade I pupils' classroom performance and classroom social interaction in the first quarter. The researcher will be getting the Mean Percentile Score (MPS) of the pupils from the class advisers of the double-shift and single-shift classes for the first quarter. A teacher-made questionnaire was distributed to the 28 Grade I teachers to determine the well-being of the pupils.

Research Instrument

The first instrument measured pupils' academic performance with the following equivalent numerical value and level:

Equivalent Numerical Value	Level
90% and above	Advanced
85% – 89%	Proficient
80% – 84%	Approaching Proficiency
75% – 79%	Developing
74% and below	Beginning

The second instrument measured the level of pupils' classroom performance and classroom social interaction with the following limits and descriptive rating.

Range	Descriptive Rating
4.21 – 5.00	Always
3.41 – 4.20	Very Often
2.61 – 3.40	Often
1.81 – 2.60	Seldom
1.00 – 1.80	Never

To establish the validity and reliability of the instruments, pilot testing was conducted in Grade II teachers in Valencia City Central School, District 1A, Division of Valencia City with the Cronbach's Alpha of .689 for the first instrument and .723 for the second instrument.

Data Gathering

To determine the level of academic performance of Grade I pupils in double-shift and single-shift classes in core subjects such as GMRC, Language, Reading and Literacy, Makabansa, and Mathematics, classroom performance, and classroom social interactions in the first quarter, mean and standard deviation were computed.

Data Analysis

To determine the significant difference in academic performance of Grade I pupils in double-shift and single-shift classes in core subjects such as GMRC, Language, Reading and Literacy, Makabansa, and Mathematics, classroom performance, and classroom social interaction in the first quarter, t-test was used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The presentation of gathered data follows the sequence of the problems posed by the study.

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Level
1. GMRC	79.33	3.51	Developing
2. Language	76.00	2.64	Developing
3. Reading and Literacy	74.67	1.53	Developing
4. Makabansa	74.00	3.60	Beginning
5. Mathematics	78.67	1.53	Developing
OVERALL MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION —		2.56	Developing

Legend: Range	Equivalent Numerical Value	Level
4.21-5.00	90% and above	Advanced
3.41-4.20	85%-89%	Proficient
2.61-3.40	80%-84%	Approaching Proficiency
1.81-2.60	75%-79%	Developing
1.00-1.80	74% and below	Beginning

The table reveals that in the double-shift classes, the academic performance of Grade I pupils in all indicators has an overall mean of 76.53 and a standard deviation of 2.56 with a level of developing. GMRC has the highest mean of 79.33 with a level of developing. This is followed by Mathematics which has a mean of 78.67, with a level of developing. Then has a mean of 74.67 with a level of developing and lastly, the Makabansa has the lowest mean of 74, with a level of developing. The results show that in double-shift classes pupils performed better in GMRC, Mathematics, and Language subjects. Pupils also performed least in Makabansa.

Table 2 presents the level of academic performance of Grade I pupils in double-shift classes. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to treat the data.

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Level
1. GMRC	75.33	0.58	Developing
2. Language	75.67	3.78	Developing
3. Reading and Literacy	77.33	0.58	Developing
4. Makabansa	75.33	4.93	Developing
5. Mathematics	76.67	3.78	Developing
OVERALL MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION	76.07	2.73	Developing

Legend: Range	Equivalent Numerical Value	Level
4.21-5.00	90% and above	Advanced
3.41-4.20	85%-89%	Proficient
2.61-3.40	80%-84%	Approaching Proficiency
1.81-2.60	75%-79%	Developing
1.00-1.80	74% and below	Beginning

The table reveals that in the single-shift classes, the academic performance of Grade I pupils has an overall mean of 76.07 with a level of developing and an overall standard deviation of 2.73. Reading and Literacy has the highest mean of 77.33 with a level of developing. This is followed by Mathematics which has a mean of 76.67 with a level of developing. Then, GMRC and Makabansa have the lowest mean of

75.33, with a level of developing. The results indicate that pupils have higher academic performance in Reading and literacy compared to other subjects.

The significant difference in the academic performance of Grade I pupils in double-shift and single-shift classes

Table 3 presents the significant difference in the academic performance of Grade I pupils in double- shift and single-shift class programs. A T-test was used to treat the data.

Table 3. *The significant difference in the academic performance of Grade I pupils in double-shift and single-shift classes.*

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Double-Shift Classes	76.53	3.18			
Single-Shift Classes	76.06	2.89	-0.504	0.622	Not Significant

The table reveals no significant difference in the academic performance of double shift and single shift classes with a p-value of .622 which indicates no significant difference. Therefore, this result gives the idea that pupils attending classes in double-shift and single-shift have the same academic performance.

Level of pupils' classroom performance of Grade I pupils in double-shift and single-shift classes

Table 4 presents the level of pupils' classroom performance of Grade I pupils in double-shift classes. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to treat the data.

Table 4. *Level of pupils' classroom performance of Grade I pupils in double-shift classes.*

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Rating
1. Attentive to class instruction	3.00	0.61	Often
2. Cooperates/participates in class	3.03	0.58	Often
3. Works up to his/her potential	2.82	0.66	Often
4. Responsive to the tasks given	2.90	0.69	Often
5. Focuses on classroom activities	3.11	0.79	Often
6. Completes assigned works	2.90	0.79	Often
7. Performs satisfactorily on tests	2.93	0.72	Often
8. Attends classes regularly	2.93	0.77	Often
9. Attentive in group/pair reading	2.90	0.69	Often
10. Collaborates in doing tasks with classmates	2.97	0.74	Often
OVERALL MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION	2.94	0.70	Often

Legend:	Range	Descriptive Rating
	3.41-4.20	Very Often
	2.61-3.40	Often
	1.81-2.60	Seldom
	1.00-1.80	Never

The table reveals that the classroom performance of the double-shift classes has an overall mean of 2.94, which is described as often, and has an overall standard deviation of .70. Pupils' focus on classroom activities has the highest mean of 3.11, which is described as often. This is followed by being cooperative and participative in class a mean of 3.03 which is described as often. Then they are attentive to class instruction has a mean of 3.00, which is described as often. Pupils who work up to their potential and are attentive in group/pair reading have the lowest mean of 2.82, which is described as often. The results indicate that pupils in double-shift classes have a focus on classroom activities, are cooperative and

participative in class, and are attentive to class instruction. In contrast to the indicators with the highest mean, pupils are not working to their potential and are less attentive in group or pair reading.

Table 5 presents the level of pupils' classroom performance of Grade I pupils in single-shift classes. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to treat the data.

Table 5. *Level of pupils' classroom performance of Grade I pupils in single-shift classes.*

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Rating
1. Attentive to class instruction	2.89	0.74	Often
2. Cooperates/participates in class	2.96	0.74	Often
3. Works up to his/her potential	2.93	0.86	Often
4. Responsive to the tasks given	3.14	0.75	Often
5. Focuses on classroom activities	3.03	0.88	Often
6. Completes assigned works	3.07	0.98	Often
7. Performs satisfactorily on tests	3.10	0.87	Often
8. Attends classes regularly	3.90	0.92	Often
9. Attentive in group/pair reading	2.75	0.89	Often
10. Collaborates in doing tasks with classmates	2.79	0.87	Often
OVERALL MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION	3.05	0.85	Often

Legend: Range Descriptive Rating

3.41-4.20	Very Often
2.61-3.40	Often
1.81-2.60	Seldom
1.00-1.80	Never

The table reveals that the classroom performance of the single-shift classes has an overall mean of 3.05, which is described as often, and has an overall standard deviation of .85. Pupils attending classes regularly have the highest mean of 3.90, which is described as often. This is followed by being responsive to the tasks given and has a mean of 3.14, which is described as often. Then pupils perform satisfactorily on tests has a mean of 3.10, which is described as often. Pupils who are attentive in group or pair reading have a lowest mean of 2.75, which is described as often. The result shows that pupils in single-shift classes attend classes regularly, are responsive to tasks given, and perform satisfactorily on tests. Pupils' attentiveness in group or pair reading is less performed by pupils.

The significant difference in classroom performance and classroom social interactions of Grade I pupils in double-shift and single-shift class session programs

Table 8 presents the significant difference in classroom performance of Grade I pupils in double-shift and single-shift classes. A T-test was used to treat the data.

Table 8. *The significant difference in classroom performance of Grade I pupils in double-shift and single-shift classes*

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Double-Shift Classes	29.64	5.75			
Single-Shift Classes	29.57	7.52	0.052	0.959	Not Significant

The table reveals that there is no significant difference in classroom performance of Grade I pupils in double-shift and single-shift classes with a p-value of .959 which indicates that there is no significant difference. The result shows that both double-shift and single-shift classes have the same classroom performance.

Level of Classroom Social Interaction of Grade I Pupils in Double and Single-Shift Class Programs.

Table 6 presents the level of pupils’ classroom social interactions of Grade I pupils in double-shift classes. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to treat the data.

Table 6. *Level of pupils’ classroom social interaction of Grade I pupils in double-shift classes.*

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Rating
1. Relates positively to teachers	3.07	0.60	Often
2. Relates positively to peers	3.10	0.57	Often
3. Communicates own needs or asks questions	2.93	0.72	Often
4. Accepts assistance when needed or offered	2.96	0.74	Often
5. Comfortable in dealing with his/her classmates	2.96	0.64	Often
6. Comfortable in the classroom environment	2.96	0.70	Often
7. Positive attitude towards school	2.96	0.74	Often
8. Creates norms in dealing with classmates	3.00	0.67	Often
9. Copes with challenges inside the classroom	2.93	0.77	Often
10. Deals with his/her classmates politely	3.00	0.67	Often
OVERALL MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION	2.99	0.68	Often

Legend:	Range	Descriptive Rating
	3.41-4.20	Very Often
	2.61-3.40	Often
	1.81-2.60	Seldom
	1.00-1.80	Never

The table reveals that in the classroom social interaction of the double-shift classes has an overall mean of 2.99, which is described as often. Pupils who relate positively to peers have the highest mean with a mean of 3.10, which is described as often. This is followed by relating positively to teachers with a mean of 3.07, which is described as often. Then, creating norms and politely dealing with their classmates has a mean of 3.0, which is described as often. Finally, coping with challenges inside the classroom has the lowest mean of 2.93, which is described as often. The results show that pupils relate positively to peers and teachers, and manifest good behavior in dealing with their classmates. Furthermore, they have difficulty in coping with challenges inside the classroom which indicates the lowest mean.

Table 7 presents the level of pupils’ classroom social interactions of Grade I pupils in single-shift classes. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to treat the data.

Table 7. *Level of pupils’ classroom social interaction of Grade I pupils in single-shift classes.*

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Rating
1. Relates positively to teachers	3.00	0.86	Often
2. Relates positively to peers	3.07	0.72	Often
3. Communicates own needs or asks questions	2.75	0.89	Often
4. Accepts assistance when needed or offered	2.89	0.79	Often
5. Comfortable in dealing with his/her classmates	2.92	0.81	Often
6. Comfortable in the classroom environment	3.03	0.84	Often
7. Positive attitude towards school	3.03	0.79	Often
8. Creates norms in dealing with his/her classmates	3.03	0.88	Often

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Rating
9. Copes with challenges inside the classroom	2.89	0.74	Often
10. Deals with his/her teacher politely	2.92	0.72	Often
OVERALL MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION	2.95	0.80	Often

Legend: Range	Descriptive Rating
3.41-4.20	Very Often
2.61-3.40	Often
1.81-2.60	Seldom
1.00-1.80	Never

The table reveals that in the classroom social interaction of the single-shift classes has an overall mean is 2.95 and an overall standard deviation of .80, which is in the level of developing. Relating positively to peers has the highest mean of 3.07, which is in the level of developing. Then followed by being comfortable in the classroom environment, positive attitude towards school, and creating norms in dealing with their classmates with a mean of 3.03, which is in the level of developing. It is also followed by relating with their teacher politely with a mean of 3.00, which is in the level of developing. Communicating their own needs or asking questions has the lowest mean of 2.75, which is in the level of developing. The results show that pupils can relate to their peers, are comfortable in the classroom environment, and have a positive attitude towards schools. However, they are not good at communicating their own needs or asking questions.

The significant difference in classroom social interactions of Grade I pupils in double-shift and single-shift classes

Table 9 presents the significant difference in classroom social interaction of Grade I pupils in double-shift and single-shift classes. A T-test was used to treat the data.

Table 9. *The significant difference in classroom social interactions of Grade I pupils in double-shift and single-shift classes*

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Double-Shift Classes	29.89	5.56			
Single-Shift Classes	29.57	6.59	0.225	0.824	Not Significant

The table reveals that there is no significant difference in the classroom social interaction of grade I pupils in double and single-shift classes with a p-value of .824 which shows no significant difference. The result shows that the Grade I double-shift and single-shift classes have the same classroom social interaction.

CONCLUSION

1. Grade I pupils in double-shift and single-shift classes have developing levels in academic performance, classroom performance, and in classroom social interaction.
2. Grade I pupils in double-shift and single-shift classes have no significant difference in academic performance, classroom performance, and classroom social interaction.

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